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HARMONY OF UZBEK AND WORLD TERMINOLOGY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS (BASED ON THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR)

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Abstract: This article analyzes the historical stages of the study of terminology issues in world linguistics, approaches and modern theoretical views. The formation and development dynamics of terminology as a scientific direction in various linguistic schools are highlighted.

Keywords: term, world terminology, uzbek terminology, classical terminology, normative-linguistic aspect, adaptation, innovation, cognitive linguistics, corporate analysis, standardization.

INTRODUCTION

Terminology is a set of language units that form the main conceptual apparatus of each scientific field, profession or area of social activity. Scientific interest in terms in linguistics began to take a serious turn from the beginning of the 20th century. The first major studies in this area were mainly aimed at standardizing terms used in the fields of technical and natural sciences. During this period, the formation of terms in different languages, their systematicity, hierarchy, semantic and structural features took shape as a separate scientific direction. In world linguistics, terminology issues are a separate area of linguistics that studies issues related to the formation, structure, meaning and use of terms (terms) used in scientific, technical, social and other fields.

In today's era of globalization, the linguistic development of each field is directly dependent on terminological harmony and accuracy. Especially in one of the main sectors of the national economy, such as agriculture, a correct and uniform understanding of terminology is important. And the harmony of the national language with world experience is the key to progress in this field, the adoption of innovations and success in international cooperation.[6,72] Agriculture is one of the most ancient and important areas of human activity, and the terms associated with its development are also constantly updated. The formation and development of agricultural terminology on a global scale is of great importance in strengthening scientific and practical ties between different languages and cultures. Horticulture is an important branch of agriculture, which is engaged in the cultivation of fruits and vegetables, the care of gardens and their economically efficient management. Horticultural terminology studies the special terms used in this field. The study of horticultural terminology on a global scale is of great scientific and practical importance. A number of international organizations play an important role in the formation and development of horticultural terminology. For example, the AGROVOC dictionary created by the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) also includes terms in the field of horticulture. AGROVOC is a multilingual controlled dictionary, which includes more than 42,000 concepts and is available in more than 42 languages. The AGRIS (Agricultural Science and Technology) system is also an important source for collecting and disseminating scientific information on horticultural sciences. This system contains scientific articles and studies related to horticulture. Horticultural terminology is an important tool not only for linguistics, but also for economic, scientific, legal and technological fields.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

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Terminology is a means of clearly expressing, organizing and generalizing concepts in science, technology, education and other fields. Although each national language has formed its own system of terms, the general development of world terminology requires coordination of this area at the global level. In this regard, world terminology and Uzbek terminology are important as complementary systems expressing modern scientific thought. One of the first scientists to form terminology as a scientific discipline was the Austrian Eugen Wuster, who gave a scientific basis to the term "terminology" in the 1930s. He is considered one of the founders of the Vienna School. This school studied the issues of standardization and classification of terms. Wuster, seeing terminology as the main tool of special sciences, developed the methodology of this discipline through the "General Theory of Terminology". He put forward the concept of "classical terminology" and emphasized that terms should be clear, concise, and unambiguous. At the same time, terminological research was also conducted in linguistics in the pre-independence years, and scientists such as A.A.Reformatsky, V.V. Vinogradov, L.A.Novikov, S.V.Grinev, T.L.Kandelaki, A.V.Superanskaya, V.M.Leychik, etc. strengthened this area. Also, the development of terminology was inextricably linked with other disciplines: philosophy (concept and term relations), cognitive linguistics (concept maps), computer science (term base), translation studies (multilingual compatibility) gave impetus to terminological research. In world linguistics, there are the following approaches to terminology issues: onomasiological, semasiological, systematic, translation-terminological approach. In European countries, especially in Germany, France, and Switzerland, the normative-linguistic aspects of terminology have been studied in depth. In the United States, a more practical direction of terminology has developed.

Our research shows that global attention to terminology issues opens up many opportunities. First, it ensures global communication, in particular, global terminology facilitates international scientific exchange, technological cooperation and professional integration. For example, terms developed in English, German or French are used in a single context throughout the world. Second, it leads to the standardization of the language of science and technology, that is, standard terms developed by international organizations (FAO, IATE, UNESCO) generalize scientific and technical languages. This ensures accuracy in multilingual projects, documents and scientific works. Most importantly, it ensures accuracy and efficiency in translation. After all, global terminology, especially in translation, prevents errors. There are special term bases for each field (for example, AGROVOC, IATE), which are an important resource for translators and specialists.

Uzbek terminology has several direct advantages: It reflects national thinking and culture, that is, the terminology of each language is associated with its historical development, thinking, and scientific tradition. Uzbek terminology reflects the approach of its people to science, word formation methods, and national identity. It is also a key tool in education and scientific research, and the presence of national terminology is very important for textbooks, dictionaries, and scientific works in the Uzbek language. This serves to form an independent approach to the development of science. In addition, it adapts terms in the national context. Uzbek linguists are not limited to simply translating foreign terms, but are adapting them to the morphological and semantic system of our language and creating new terms. The rich experience of world terminology is entering Uzbek terminology through reliance, translation, and adaptation. At the same time, Uzbek linguists are also forming their own national terminology school. This process takes place in two directions:

Adaptation - adapting international terms to the Uzbek language; Innovation - developing new terms in the Uzbek language.

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DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In world linguistics, terminology issues are considered a key tool in many fields, such as science, technology, law, medicine, and computer science. In recent years, terminology has been developing in tandem with modern technologies. In particular, the practice of creating term banks based on corpus linguistics, computer terminology, multimodal term dictionaries, and terminological networks based on ontologies. This strengthens the integration of terminology not only with linguistics, but also with disciplines related to computer science and knowledge engineering. In scientific fields, terms must have a single meaning and a clear definition. This ensures their clarity and reliability. Currently, terminology is actively studied in the following areas:

- Computational linguistics - automatic recognition and classification of terms
- Cognitive linguistics - the relationship of terms to concept maps and knowledge models
- Corporative analysis - the study of the dynamics of terms in large corpuses of texts
- Multilingual terminology - multilingual term bases and translation problems.

CONCLUSION

In general, terminological research in world linguistics is carried out on the basis of various theoretical approaches and remains relevant today. Terminology is becoming an area that requires special attention as a specific means of forming scientific thinking, standardizing communication and transmitting information. This further strengthens its place in the development of each field. Today, the science of terminology is relevant not only in theoretical, but also in practical areas. The scientific approaches formed in world linguistics have been enriched with their own directions in Uzbek linguistics. Dictionaries, scientific developments and terminological analyses created by Uzbek scientists directly influence language policy, translation practice, the development of the language of science and information technologies. World and Uzbek terminology are complementary systems. While world terminology serves the development of science and technology on an international scale, Uzbek terminology is the basis of national thinking, language development and an independent scientific approach. By combining these two directions, the Uzbek language is becoming a modern language of science. The harmony of Uzbek and world agricultural terminology is an important factor in the development of modern agricultural technologies, the development of international scientific and practical cooperation, and the increase in the scientific potential of the Uzbek language. Therefore, the systematic development of terms, their discussion with the scientific community, and the creation of dictionaries based on translations that meet the requirements of the time are urgent tasks. Terms are not just words - they are a mirror of thought, knowledge, and progress. National and international harmony of agricultural terminology contributes to the further development of this field.

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